

THE IMPORTANCE OF ENGLISH IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBALIZATION

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Abstract: This article discusses the status of the English language throughout the country and its current status. English was one of the vernacular languages in the past centuries. But today it is strengthening its position in Europe and even in the whole world.

Keywords: importance, history, language, global, impact, English, speaking, world, country, popularity, Uzbekistan.

One of the main factors of globalization is direct communication between different nations and peoples. Serious, intensive and effective study of foreign languages is important in this regard. Almost all languages of today are considered to have an original language of origin. In this regard, first of all, before studying the English language, it is necessary to know its original origin more clearly. Each language forms its own family. English belongs to the group of Indo-European languages. This language also includes French, Italian, German, Norwegian and Greek. The history of the origin of the English language dates back to the mid-5th century and began in the Anglo-Saxon region of England and the southeast of present-day Scotland, later in the kingdom of Northumbria. It is in this area that the English language originated. Later, due to the influence of the United States, it has spread throughout the world and is becoming the leading communication language in several sources. In ancient times, English was called Anglo-Saxon and split into 4 dialects, Northumbrian, Mercian, Wessex and Kent. The word English is said to be derived from the word Angles.

As of 2020, there are 1.27 billion speakers worldwide and more than 50 countries officially recognize it. However, English will not be the same. Phonetic and lexical features distinguish the speech of England, Canada, Australia and others. But this does not interfere with understanding each other in oral speech.

Today, the study of foreign languages, especially English, is gaining momentum in society. In addition to this, the language is accepted and supported worldwide and has been considered a very important global language. Learning English is not difficult for people. Because the writing and pronunciation of the language is not as complicated as other languages. There are several reasons why English has become a global language, for example, science, technology, trade, art, economics, diplomacy and other areas contribute to this. We can say for sure that no other language can match English in terms of its popularity.

In short, the English language is developing day by day and is spreading its influence all over the world. Today, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, compared to other foreign languages, English has become a very important language. One of the main reasons for this is the significant growth of the economy, the increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting the country compared to previous years, the expansion of people's travel opportunities, and the acceleration of the process of globalization throughout the world. One of the next important reasons was the news in science, the popularity of the internet. Thirdly, having a common language during

intercultural communication helps the exchange of cultures to be effective. Nevertheless, the level of English language teaching in the country is described as relatively satisfactory.

In Uzbekistan, the main field of experience for English language learners consists only of the classroom and the teacher. Given the pretertiary process, English from elementary school and high school. Paid clubs are organized in kindergartens based on the patronage of parents. Then, in Uzbekistan, children start learning English from the age of 6 on average and continue in higher education as well. Here, despite the fact that students study English for a very long time (on average they spend 1 year in kindergarten, 11 years in school, 4 to 6 years in university), students have difficulty communicating in English in a real context. According to the results of studies, the level of higher education of the population in the country is equal to 9.8%. This is the lowest among Central Asian countries is one of the indicators. In addition, the Russian invasion of Uzbekistan and the close relations in administration, economy and social sphere even after the collapse of the Soviet state led to the country's education sector being under the strong influence of this country, despite the fact that high results are recorded in learning English as a foreign language, there are various problems in teaching and learning English.

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